

We provide a potential prompt for extracting medical claims.

System Message:

You are an expert in the medical domain.

User Message:

–Goal–

Extract and analyze all relevant medical entities from the text and map the relationships among them, ensuring accurate representation.

–Steps–

1. **Entity Identification:** Extract each medical entity with the following details:

- **entity_name:** Name of the entity, always capitalized.
- **entity_type:** Category of the entity (e.g., Disease, Symptom, Drug).
- **entity_description:** A detailed description including attributes and functions.

2. **Relationship Identification:** Identify all relevant pairs of related entities and classify the relationship type based on predefined categories.

- **Types of Relationships:** ['exposure_exposure', 'protein_protein', 'pathway_protein', 'anatomy_protein_absent', 'anatomy_protein_present', 'cellcomp_protein', 'off-label use', 'cellcomp_cellcomp', 'exposure_molfunc', 'pathway_pathway', 'exposure_bioprocess', 'phenotype_protein', 'exposure_cellcomp', 'contraindication', 'exposure_protein', 'drug_effect', 'indication', 'molfunc_molfunc', 'disease_disease', 'exposure_disease', 'drug_drug', 'disease_protein', 'molfunc_protein', 'bioprocess_protein', 'disease_phenotype_negative', 'bioprocess_bioprocess', 'anatomy_anatomy', 'phenotype_phenotype', 'disease_phenotype_positive', 'drug_protein'].

3. **Relationship Validation:** Remove redundant relationships where two terms refer to the same conceptual entity to prevent overlapping or duplicate relationships.

4. **Output Generation:** Compile all validated and scored relationships into a list, formatted as:

(<source_entity >{tuple_delimiter} <target_entity>{tuple_delimiter} <relationship_description>).

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–Example–

Text: The patient's symptoms of poor urine flow and taking a long time to empty the bladder suggest a urethral obstruction, which is most likely due to a urethral stricture. The patient's previous episode of non-gonococcal urethritis may have caused scarring or inflammation leading to a stricture.

Output:

(Non-gonococcal urethritis{tuple_delimiter}Urethral stricture{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)
(Urethral obstruction{tuple_delimiter}Poor urine flow{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)
(Urethral obstruction{tuple_delimiter}Long time to empty{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)
(Urethral stricture{tuple_delimiter}Urethral obstruction{tuple_delimiter}disease_disease)
(Non-gonococcal urethritis{tuple_delimiter}Scarring{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)
(Non-gonococcal urethritis{tuple_delimiter}Inflammation{tuple_delimiter}disease_phenotype_positive)

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–Real Data–

Text: ...

Output:

Continue Prompt:

MANY entities and relationships were missed in the last extraction. Remember to ONLY emit entities that related to medicine. Add them below using the same format.

Loop Prompt:

It appears some entities and relationships may have still been missed. Answer YES — NO if there are still entities or relationships that need to be added.
